

The Study of Outcomes in Neonates Born to ABO and Rhesus (D) Incompatible Mothers

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Abstract:

Background: In this study, we wanted to study the outcomes and follow up of ABO and Rh(D) incompatible neonates, to study the incidence of ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting, to follow up the neonates with ABO and Rh(D) Incompatible setting, to study the clinical outcomes among them and to initiate a prompt treatment, to propose a discharge plan for neonates with ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting.

Methods: This was a Hospital Based Prospective Observational Study conducted among 166 neonates with ABO incompatibility and 28 neonates with Rhesus (D) incompatibility between 24 to 44 weeks of gestational age delivered at Medicit Institute of Medical Sciences, from 1st January 2021 to 30th June 2022, after obtaining clearance from Institutional ethics committee and written informed consent from the study participants.

Results: The prevalence of ABO blood groups in mothers was O > B > A > AB. The prevalence of ABO blood groups in neonates was B > O > A > AB. SGA neonates are more prone to higher serum bilirubin levels. Neonates in whom elder siblings received phototherapy are prone for higher serum bilirubin levels. There was no correlation between mean serum bilirubin value and sex of the neonate. There was no correlation between mean serum bilirubin value and maternal factors like mode of the delivery and age of the mother. There was no significant difference in hyperbilirubinemia between OA and OB incompatible setting. Severity of hemolysis was more among neonates with Rh(D) incompatible setting than ABO incompatible setting. Maximum number of admissions among neonates with incompatibility is within the first three days of life. After 3rd day of life, maximum admissions are on 6th day of life. Early identification of ABO and Rh(D) incompatibility reduced the mortality and morbidity due to hyperbilirubinemia. Phototherapy as a mode of treatment was found to be effective in the management of hyperbilirubinemia. However, longer duration of phototherapy was required in neonates with evidence of positive DCT among ABO incompatibility. Cord bilirubin level above 2.6mg/dl has statistically significant association with the need for phototherapy with area under curve showing 0.77.

Conclusion: As maximum number of admissions is on day 3 of life, the neonates with ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting should be observed in the postnatal ward or should be followed up every day for at least 3 days of life. As serum bilirubin again peaks on day 6 of life, there should be a follow-up visit on day 6. As cord bilirubin is a reliable predictor of hyperbilirubinemia, it should be done all neonates born to Rh negative mothers.

Keywords: Outcomes, Neonates, Abo, Rhesus(D), Incompatible Mothers.

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Introduction

Karl Landsteiner discovered ABO and Rh blood grouping systems in humans and suggested the letters O, A, B and AB to express blood groups which were universally followed. Multiple alleles of ABO blood groups are located on a single locus of long arm of ninth chromosome (9q34) that exhibit Mendelian inheritance pattern. ABO gene has mainly three types of alleles: I express no antigen hence type O, IA express type A antigen,

and IB express type B antigen where I is a designation for isoagglutinin. IAIB individual has both phenotypes due to codominance and is typed as AB blood group. Rh is the second major blood group system which comprises of more than 50 blood group antigens. Out of them, RHD and RHCE are the most clinically important Rh antigens. RHD and RHCE are closely linked genes on chromosome 1 that controls expression of Rh

proteins [1,2]. Along with discovery of ABO system, Karl Landsteiner also reported the presence of antibodies directed against the A and B antigens in the serum. Thus, individuals belonging to blood group A has antibodies against B antigen in their sera while those with group B blood has antibodies against the A antigen in their sera. Group O individuals have both anti-A and anti-B antibodies in their sera while AB cells possess neither of the antibodies.

These antibodies are referred to as iso – antibodies. Cases of hemolytic diseases do result from pregnancies involving a group A, B, and AB infants in which the mother is O group. It is said to be an important diagnosis in cases of neonatal jaundice and anemia with very severe cases requiring exchange blood transfusion. This often occurs where the infants inherit a blood group from the father that is not compatible with that of the mother, leading to the maternal response to the fetal cells [3]. ABO hemolytic disease of the newborn is the most common maternofetal blood group incompatibility. It is restricted almost entirely to group A or B babies born to group O mothers with immune anti-A or anti-B antibodies. Although, HDN has been reported in a baby whose mother was group A with high titres of anti B [4]. In general, 15-20% of all maternal/fetal pairs are ABO incompatible, but hemolytic disease of the newborn due to ABO incompatibility is confined to approximately 1% of group O mothers who have high titres of Immunoglobulin G anti A/B antibodies. Hemolysis due to anti A is more common (1 in 150) than that due to anti-B [5]. In mothers with group A or B, naturally occurring antibodies are of the IgM class and do not cross the placenta, whereas type-O mothers have anti-A and /anti-B IgG class against both A and B. High titres of IgG antibodies are present in individuals with blood group O compared to blood group A and B. The antibody production further increases after exposure to antigens. But as IgG antibodies can occur without previous red cell exposure, they can result in hemolytic disease of newborn even in first pregnancy [6].

Among group A or B infants born to group O mothers, 30-50% have detectable maternal IgG antibody bound to their red cells compared to 5% among all individuals. They cross the placenta and cause hemolysis in fetus. Although variable anti-A and anti-B titres are found in the mothers of infants with ABO hemolytic disease, usually these titers are higher than the average normal, and the antibodies are at least partly incompatible, difficult to neutralize with specific substance, and somewhat lytic in the presence of adequate human complement. Fetal RBCs appear to have less surface expression of A or B antigen, resulting in few reactive sites. Hence the low incidence of

significant hemolysis in affected neonates. This results in hyperbilirubinemia as a predominant manifestation of incompatibility (rather than anemia) and peripheral blood film frequently reveals a large number of micro spherocytes and few erythroblasts. It has been noted that hemolytic disease of the newborn due to ABO incompatibility frequently occurs during the first pregnancy, and about 50% of infants are affected unlike Rhesus hemolytic disease of the newborn in which the first born- babies are usually spared or free of the disease and subsequent babies are the ones that are affected. ABO - HDN is described as a condition having a very low incidence in the population and characterized by a benign evolution because of a mild degree of hemolysis.

The hemolytic disease of newborn also occurs due to those directed against Rh antigens (anti-D, anti-c and anti-E), anti-Kell, anti-Kidd (Jk), anti-Duffy (Fy) and antibodies of the MNS blood group system. Of these, anti-D remains the most common cause of significant haemolytic anaemia, affecting 1 in 1200 pregnancies. Anti-Kell antibodies are less common, but can cause severe fetal and neonatal anaemia as they inhibit erythropoiesis as well as causing hemolysis [7,8]

After sensitization, maternal anti-D antibodies cross the placenta into fetal circulation and attach to Rh(D) antigen on fetal RBCs, which form rosettes on macrophages in the reticuloendothelial system, especially in the spleen. These antibody-coated RBCs are lysed by lysosomal enzymes released by macrophages and natural killer lymphocytes and are independent of the activation of the complement system. Hemolytic disease rarely occurs during first pregnancy because transfusion of Rh- positive fetal blood into an Rh-negative mother occurs during the time of delivery, too late for the mother to become sensitized and transmit antibodies to her infant before delivery. [9]

When the mother and fetus are also incompatible with respect to group A or B, the mother is partially protected against sensitization by the rapid removal of RH- positive cells from her circulation by her pre-existing anti- A and anti-B, which are IgM antibodies and not cross the placenta. Fetal anemia in Rh isoimmunization occurs due to the reduced life span of erythrocytes. As RBC's are coated with antibodies and these coated antibodies are phagocytosed by reticuloendothelial cells. In severe cases of Rh isoimmunization (erythroblastosis fetalis), hydrops and heart failure are related to severe anemia in the fetus Hydrops often results in fetal or neonatal death without appropriate antenatal intervention. Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia is a common condition requiring inpatient treatment, as well as important reason for readmission to hospital.

Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia occurs in 70-80% of neonates, more commonly in preterms. When the total serum bilirubin rises above the 95th percentile for age on the hour specific bhutani nomogram it will be considered as hyperbilirubinemia. ABO and Rh(D)incompatibility is one of the most common pathological causes for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

Aims and Objectives

- To study the outcomes and follow up of ABO and Rh(D) incompatible neonates delivered at tertiary care hospital.
- To study the incidence of ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting.
- To follow up the neonates with ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting.
- To study the clinical outcomes among them and to initiate a prompt treatment.
- To propose a discharge plan for neonates with ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting.

Methods

This was a hospital based prospective observational study conducted among 166 neonates with ABO incompatibility and 28 neonates with Rhesus(D) incompatibility between 24 to 44 weeks of gestational age delivered at MediCiti Institute of Medical Sciences, from 1st January 2021 to 30th June 2022, after obtaining clearance from institutional ethics committee and written informed consent from the study participants.

Inclusion Criteria: All live born neonates between 24 to 44 weeks of gestational age delivered at Mediciti institute of Medical Sciences during the study period.

Exclusion Criteria

- Intra uterine deaths.
- Still born.
- Neonates delivered outside MIMS.
- Statistical Methods

Data was entered into Microsoft Excel sheet and analyzed using SPSS Statistical Software.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of cases according to parity of Mother

Mode of delivery	Normal vaginal delivery	OFD	LSCS	Total (n)		
ABO	83(50%)	17(10%)	66(40%)	166(100%)		
Rh(D)	12(43%)	3(10%)	13(46%)	28(100%)		
Mode of deliveries among ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting neonates						
Incompatibility	ELBW	VLBW	LBW	Normal	Macrosomia	Total(n)
ABO	0	0	26(15%)	140(85%)	0	166(100%)
Rh(D)	0	0	8(28%)	20(72%)	0	28(100%)
Distribution of neonates according to their birth weight						
	SGA	AGA	LGA	Total (n)		
ABO(n=166)	26 (15%)	138 (84%)	2 (1%)	166(100%)		
Rh(D)(n=28)	10 (36%)	18 (64%)	-	28(100%)		
Distribution of neonates according to weight and gestational age						
PERIOD OF GESTATION		ABO(n=166)	Rh(n=28)			
Very Preterm		0 (0%)	0 (0%)			
Moderate Preterm		2 (1.2%)	0 (0%)			
Late Preterm		9 (5.4%)	2 (7.1%)			
Early Term		90 (54.3%)	15 (53.5%)			
Full Term		65 (39.1%)	11 (39.4%)			
Total (n)		166 (100%)	28 (100%)			
Distribution of neonates according to gestational age						
Parity Of Mother	Para 1	Para 2	Para 3	Para 4	Total (n)	Abortions (1)
ABO (n=166)	76 (46%)	81 (49%)	9 (5%)	0	166	11
Rh(D) (n=28)	10 (36%)	14 (50%)	4 (14%)	0	28	4

- In ABO incompatibility normal vaginal deliveries are more than LSCS.
- In Rh(D) incompatibility combined normal vaginal and instrumental deliveries are more than LSCS.
- There are no ELBW, VLBW and macrosomic neonates in both ABO and Rh(D)incompatible setting.
- The incidence of LBW is more in Rh(D) incompatible setting.

- There are no LGA neonates in Rh(D) incompatibility
- The incidence of SGA neonates are more in Rh(D) than ABO incompatibility
- There are no very preterms in both ABO and Rh(D) incompatible setting There are no moderate preterms in Rh(D) incompatible setting
- There are a greater number of multiparous mothers in both ABO and Rh(D)incompatible neonates

Table 2: Clinical staging of icterus according to KRAMER'S ZONES among followed up neonates

No. Mothers received Blood Transfusion	No. of Mother's			Percentage			
ABO (n=166)	2			1.20%			
Rh(D) (n=28)	1			3.50%			
Showing number of mothers with ABO &/or Rh(D) incompatible setting who received Blood Transfusions							
Incompatibility setting	No of babies			Percentage			
OA	16			25%			
OB	36			56%			
Rh setting	12			19%			
Total (N)	64			100%			
Showing blood group incompatible setting among previous babies							
Mother's Age	<20	20-30	>30	Total (n)			
ABO(n=166)	12 (7%)	142 (85%)	12 (7%)	166(100%)			
Rh(D)(n=28)	-	26 (92%)	2 (8%)	28(100%)			
Distribution of cases according to age of mother							
	Male	Term	Normal Birth Weight	Primi	Multi	Model of Delivery: OFD	Model of Delivery: LSCS
No. of Babies	2	2	2	1	1	1	1
Demographic details of Neonates with both ABO & Rh incompatibility setting							
Day of examination	Total babies examined			percentage			
DAY 1	192			100%			
DAY 2	191			99%			
DAY 3	186			96%			
DAY 6	180			93%			
DAY 10	172			89%			
Total number of babies followed up according to day of life							
Kramer's Zone	DAY 1 (n=192)	DAY 2 (n=191)	DAY 3 (n=186)	DAY 6 (n=180)	DAY 10 (n=172)		
NIL	98	19		31	75		
FACE and neck	59	61	38	42	63		
Chest and upper abdomen	27	44	51	74	12		
Lower Abdomen and thighs	7	43	62	21	15		
Legs and arms/forearms	1	14	12	5	4		
Palms and soles	-	2	7	3	2		
No. of Babies bleached	-	8	16	4	1		

- All the blood transfusions are during antenatal period due to anemia in the mother
- No. of previous babies admitted & received Phototherapy: 30
- There are no teenage pregnancies among Rh(D) incompatible neonate's mothers
- Majority of the mothers are at optimal age of conception
- Both the neonates are admitted for phototherapy
- 20 neonates (11%) lost to follow up by the end of the study period

Table 3: Total number of NNH admissions (with/without ABO and/or Rh(D) incompatibility) during study period

Day	Avg. Bilirubin among admitted	Avg. Bilirubin among not admitted
Day 0 (Cord Blood)	0.00	2.31(n=31)
Day 1	8.89(n=8)	0.00
Day 2	13.85(n=16)	9.05(n=2)
Day 3	16.31(n=19)	10.50(n=97)
Day 4	17.00(n=1)	11.70(n=2)
Day 5	15.60(n=1)	9.07(n=3)
Day 6	16.24(n=5)	10.31(n=34)
Day 7	0.00	0.00
Day 8	0.00	0.00

Day 9	16.80(n=1)	0.00
Day 10	15.95(n=2)	9.42(n=5)
Showing average Bilirubin value – among all neonates with ABO and/or Rh(D) incompatible setting		
Blood group incompatibility	Total no. of babies	Percentage
ABO (n = 166)	63	38%
Rh (n = 28)	3	11%
Total (n)	66	100%
Number of admissions according to blood group incompatibility		
ABO Incompatible setting	Total no. of Babies	No. of Babies Admitted
OA	59	21
OB	107	42
Total (n)	166	63
Showing ABO incompatible setting Analysis among Admitted babies		
Reason for admission	No. of Babies admitted (n = 66)	Percentage
NNH	59	89%
Other causes	7	11%
Showing neonates admitted with NNH or other causes		
Total Number of NNH admissions	No. of babies with ABO and Rh incompatibility	Percentage
182	66	36%

- Maximum number of admissions for phototherapy are at 3rd day of life There are no admissions on day 7 and day 8 of life
- Serum bilirubin mean among not admitted babies gradually increased till day 4 then it reduced following similar pattern of physiological jaundice
- Maximum percentage of admissions are among neonates with ABO incompatibility rather than Rh(D) incompatibility
- There is no significance difference for admission among OA and OB incompatible setting neonates
- Maximum number of neonates are admitted for hyperbilirubinemia
- ABO and / or Rh(D) incompatible setting is one of the major causes for admission with hyperbilirubinemia.

Table 4: Showing Day of Admission Analysis of Neonates with ABO And / or Rh(D) Incompatible Setting

Day Of Admission	Number Of Babies	Percentage
At Birth	6	9%
Day 1	14	21%
Day 2	16	24%
Day 3	19	29%
Day 4	1	2%
Day 5	1	2%
Day 6	6	9%
Day 7	0	0%
Day 8	0	0%
Day 9	1	2%
Day 10	2	3%
Total (N)	66	100%

Maximum number of admissions for phototherapy is at 3rd day of life There are no admissions on day 7 and day 8 of life. Even though there are 6 admissions immediately after birth, the reason for admission is other than hyperbilirubinemia.

Table 5: Showing risk stratification among admitted cases - According to gestational age

Sex of the Baby	No of neonates	Percentage
Male	33	50%
Female	33	50%
Total (n)	66	100%

Showing risk stratification among admitted cases - According to sex		
Mode Of Delivery	Total	Percentage
Normal Vaginal Delivery	35	53%
LSCS	31	47%
Total (n)	66	100%
Showing risk stratification among admitted cases - According to mode of delivery		
Weight	Total no. of Babies Admitted	Percentage
SGA	16	24%
AGA	48	73%
LGA	2	3%
Total (n)	66	100%
Showing risk stratification among admitted cases - According to weight		
Parity	Total no. of Babies Admitted	Percentage
Primi	33	50%
Multi	33	50%
Total (n)	66	100%
Showing risk stratification among admitted cases - According to parity of mother		
Gestation	Total no. of Babies Admitted	Percentage
Preterm	7	10.6%
Term	59	89.4%
Total (n)	66	100%

Table 6: showing number of phototherapy surfaces used among admitted babies for NNH

Age of mother	Total no. of Babies Admitted	Percentage
< 20	7	10.6%
20-30	51	77.2%
>30	8	12.2%
Total (n)	66	100%
Showing risk stratification among admitted cases - According to age of mother		
	Count	Percentage
Dehydration	5	8%
Preterm	7	11%
Sepsis	8	12%
Birth asphyxia	2	3%
Cephalhematoma	0	0%
IUGR	16	24%
Without aggravating factors	28	42%
Total (n)	66	100%
Showing aggravating Conditions for hyperbilirubinemia among neonates with ABO and/or Rh(D) incompatibility		
Mode Of Treatment	Total Babies (n=59)	Percentage
Phototherapy	59	98.31%
Exchange Transfusion	1	1.69%
Pharmacological Therapy (pheno-barbitone)	-	-
Showing treatment modalities among admitted babies for NNH		
Phototherapy Surface	No of neonates	Percentage
Single	4	7%
Double	52	88%
Triple	3	5%
Total (n)	59	100%

IUGR is the major aggravating condition for hyperbilirubinemia followed by prematurity, Phototherapy is the major mode of treatment for hyperbilirubinemia, Only one neonate underwent exchange transfusion in Rh(D) incompatible group, None of them received pharmacological therapy, Maximum number of neonates received double surface, phototherapy Only 3 neonates required intensive phototherapy.

Table 7: Showing number of neonates who are DCT positive among ABO incompatible and Rh(D) incompatible setting

Duration of Treatment (hrs)	Number of neonates		
18	2		
24	48		
48	7		
96	2		
Total (n)	59		
Showing duration of phototherapy given			
Component	Total No. of Babies	Percentage	
Anemia	1	1.52%	
Reticulocytosis	8	12.12%	
Microspherocytes	9	13.63%	
showing severity of hemolysis among neonates admitted with NNH			
Incompatible setting	Number of neonates with incompatible setting	No of neonates with DCT positive	Percentage
ABO	166	6	3.6%
Rh(D)	28	3	10.71%
Total	194	9	4.63%

Mean duration of phototherapy – 32 hours
Average Hb: 16.8 mg/dl, only one neonate has anemia.

Discussion

In the present study, the incidence of the ABO blood groups among mothers are as follows (n=1240):

- Group - 34.61 %
- A group – 17.9 %
- B group – 34.75%
- AB group – 7.76%

Over all incidence: O > B > A > AB

The incidence of the ABO blood groups among mothers in the present study is similar to the southern region according to systematic review by Gopal et al.

In the present study, the incidence of Rh-negative blood group among mothers is 5.8% which is almost similar to incidence in overall India according to systematic review by Gopal et al.

In the present study, the incidence of the ABO blood groups among neonates are as follows (n=1255):

- group: 32.11%
- A group: 20.95 %
- B group: 38.48%
- AB group: 8.46%

Overall incidence: B > O > A > AB. In the present study, the incidence of ABO incompatible setting is 13.22% which is similar to study conducted by Apexa et al (n=1450) [9] but a lower incidence (9.2%) is seen in the study by Sarhan Alshamari et al (n=9000) [10]. In the present study, the incidence of Rh(D) incompatible setting is 2.23% which is almost equal to the study conducted by Apexa et al

[11]. The incidence of Rh(D) incompatibility according to Rajeev Mehta et al study is 3.8% [12]

In the present study among 166 neonates with ABO incompatible setting, neonates with OA incompatible setting are 35.54% and OB incompatible setting are 64.46% which is similar to studies by Snehalatha Gopu et al [13] and Vijaya s kattamani et al. In the present study there is no significant difference in the development of hyperbilirubinemia among neonates with OA and OB incompatible setting with P value 0.81. Similar observation is seen in Snehalatha et al and Ella E et al study.

In the present study, there is no correlation between mean serum bilirubin level and sex of the neonate. Correlation coefficient (Spearman's rank correlation) is 0.05. The observation is similar to the studies by Vijaya s kattamani et al, Kumar A et al, Akgul S, Shah A and Preethi et al [14-17]. Male neonates have higher serum bilirubin levels according to studies by Mantani et al, Sharma et al [18,19].

In the present study, mean serum bilirubin levels are similar among SGA, AGA and LGA neonates. The interquartile range for SGA babies are 12.5, 14 and 16 at 25%, 50% and 75% respectively indicating that SGA neonates are slightly prone to higher serum bilirubin levels. Similar observation is seen in Nepal D et al and Chaudhary et al [20,21].

In the present study, neonates born to Primi parous mothers has higher mean serum bilirubin values compared to multiparous mothers determined by performing a T test (parity being taken as continuous categorical variable) with a P value 0.049. In studies conducted by Shah et al and Kalakheti et al [22] there is no statistical significance between serum bilirubin levels and parity of the mother.

In the present study, there is no statistical signifi-

cance when mean serum bilirubin level is compared with the mode of the delivery which is determined by performing ANOVA test with a P value 0.46. It is similar to Amar et al study. [23]

In the present study, mean serum bilirubin levels are higher among neonates whose elder siblings were admitted for phototherapy determined by performing Ttest with a P value 0.01.

In the present study, out of 166 neonates with ABO incompatible setting; 6(3.6%) are DCT positive. Among 28 neonates with Rh(D) incompatible setting; 3(10.71%) are DCT positive.

In the present study, in comparison of neonates with OA and OB incompatible setting there is no statistically significant difference in the frequency of positive DCT and duration of phototherapy between the two groups. Similar results are obtained in the Akgul et al study.

Conclusion

The prevalence of ABO blood groups in mothers is $O > B > A > AB$. The prevalence of ABO blood groups in neonates is $B > O > A > AB$. SGA neonates are more prone to higher serum bilirubin levels Neonates in whom elder siblings received phototherapy are prone for higher serum bilirubin levels. There is no correlation between mean serum bilirubin value and sex of the neonate. There is no correlation between mean serum bilirubin value and maternal factors like mode of the delivery and age of the mother.

There is no significant difference in hyperbilirubinemia between OA and OB incompatible setting. Severity of hemolysis is more among neonates with Rh(D) incompatible setting than ABO incompatible setting. Maximum number of admissions among neonates with incompatibility is within the first three days of life. After 3rd day of life, maximum admissions are on 6th day of life. Early identification of ABO and Rh(D) incompatibility reduced the mortality and morbidity due to hyperbilirubinemia. Phototherapy as a mode of treatment was found to be effective in the management of hyperbilirubinemia.

However, longer duration of phototherapy was required in neonates with evidence of positive DCT among ABO incompatibility. Cord bilirubin level above 2.6mg/dl has statistically significant association with the need for phototherapy with area under curve showing 0.77.

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